

NORMS OF RELIGIOUS AND MORAL UPBRINGING OF CHILDREN

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Annotation

In the article, the author commented on the importance of education and upbringing for the future of the society, first of all, it is necessary to promote spirituality in the family and at the same time pay great attention to the upbringing of spiritual enlightenment in education. Since ancient times, in the issues of education, it has been emphasized that religious education, which serves to perfect the feelings of humanity, patriotism, respect for parents, and mutual affection between people, will bring positive results if examples are given from the verses of the Holy Qur'an, hadiths and narrations of various religious content.

Key words: education and upbringing, environment, ancestors, religion, spirituality, family, advice, hadith, virtue.

At present, the issue of educating moral principles and spirituality among young people is a pressing issue. Religious education has contributed to the restoration of spirituality and enlightenment qualities that are valuable for any society.

We understand very well how true the words of the well-known enlightener Abdulla Avloni are: "Education is a matter of life - or death, or salvation - or destruction, or happiness - or disaster" for us. Education is the process of imparting certain behavioral skills to a child in his growing environment. The center of education is a school, but the first school of a child is the embrace of his own family.

Raising spirituality in the family.

Our great compatriot Imam Ghazali says: "Children are a trust given to their

parents. A child's heart is a precious gem without any pattern. It accepts whatever pattern is made, and bends wherever it is bent. If he is taught to be good, he will grow and achieve happiness in this world and the hereafter. His parents and every teacher will share his reward. If they are made to do evil, if they are left to their own devices like animals, they will eventually perish. And his guilt falls on the shoulders of those who are responsible for his education.

Good manners and good habits are inculcated in the child at an early age, so that it will be easier for him to live in adulthood. It is important not only to teach the principles of behavior, but also to convey their meaning and values to children in an understandable way.

Along with the basic scientific and educational education in the family, religious education is the basis of the child's moral formation. By observing religious laws and rules in the family, reading religious books together, celebrating religious holidays and visiting ancient monuments, it is possible to gently correct the behavior of children. By religious rules and laws, we mean the "Hadith" books, which contain morals and educational norms in the form of advice, not fixed laws. Hadith (Arabic - message, saying, news) is a narration about the words, actions and confessions of Muhammad (peace be upon him). [1].

An important thing in religious education and upbringing is the moral image of parents and older relatives. Only a personal positive example can explain the importance of family and religious traditions to the child's soul. In religion, special attention is paid to concepts such as good and evil, the meaning of life and the importance of a person with spiritual principles and values.

Spiritual enlightenment in education

Over the past years, a number of reforms aimed at improving the quality of religious education have been implemented in our republic, as in other countries of the world. As part of the measures aimed at the organization and development of the

religious education system in accordance with world standards, first of all, normative legal documents related to religious education were developed.

In general secondary schools and lyceum-colleges in Uzbekistan, in subjects such as "Religion", "History of World Religions", detailed information about several religions and their prayers, as well as in subjects such as "Etiquette", "Basics of Spirituality", "Uzbek Literature" should be given to each person. It is necessary to mention that there are many topics, examples of which are provided from the Qur'anic verses, hadith sharif and narrations of various religious content, which serve to perfect the feelings of mutual affection between people, humanity, patriotism, respect for parents. This naturally raises questions such as why religious information about Islam is included in school textbooks. Therefore, in approaching this issue, it is appropriate to explain that great muhaddiths like Imam Bukhari and Imam Termizi, who were among the main reasons for the transmission of those hadiths to the entire Muslim world, are the ancestors of the local population living in this country, and studying the scientific heritage left by them is a sacred duty of the children of this country. [2].

Along with culture and enlightenment, the concept of religion in the direction of education and training should serve to shape children's worldview. Respecting the independence of world religions, studying the composition and origin of Orthodoxy, Buddhism, Islam, and Judaism, and making effective use of the incomparable information corresponding to universal moral standards in their personal development is one of the most important issues.

This issue reveals the foundations of different religions, the connection between religious traditions and the ethics of the peoples of the world, and in its place creates the education of patriotism and tolerance in young people.

It is impossible to form a person as a full-fledged person without cultivating moral qualities in him. External and internal factors have a great influence on the

moral characteristics of young people.

It is necessary to purposefully develop such feelings and character qualities as honesty, justice, respect for people, striving for creativity and mental and physical improvement in the child from the first years of life.

As we bring up the young generation through religious education, we ourselves become richer in meaning and reach perfection once again. Religious education is the basis for serving the interests of our nation by raising self-confidence and correctness in a child.

Literature:

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